

AI-Based Multi-Objective Optimization of Automotive Lighting Systems: A Comparative Study of Halogen, LED and Xenon Technologies

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Abstract:

The widespread use of external and internal lighting systems in the automotive industry increases energy consumption while also influencing visual comfort and driving safety. Conventional halogen, xenon, and modern LED technologies differ in luminous intensity, color quality, and long-term stability. In this study, experimental measurement data of 16 automotive lighting products (H1, H3, H7; 12 V–55 W and 24 V–70 W; halogen, LED, and xenon) were re-analyzed using an artificial intelligence–driven optimization framework. Laboratory measurements include luminous intensity (lux), color temperature, dominant wavelength, and long-term degradation over 300 hours.

We propose a multi-objective optimization model with three conflicting objectives: maximizing luminous intensity, maximizing color quality, and minimizing energy consumption and degradation. Feature vectors were constructed from the experimental dataset (lamp type, technology, voltage, power, luminous intensity, degradation percentage, and color quality score). A non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) was applied to identify Pareto-optimal solutions. Comparative baselines were defined using single-objective rankings such as lux/W and color rendering index.

Preliminary analysis shows that 24 V halogen lamps achieve higher absolute lux values (≈ 185 –195 lx), but LED lamps outperform in terms of stability and color quality, maintaining or even increasing luminous intensity after 300 hours. Xenon samples deliver lower luminous efficiency (≈ 71 –89 lx at 70 W). Pareto-front analysis highlights LED H1 at 12 V as a balanced solution with superior degradation resistance and sustainable energy efficiency, while halogen solutions dominate in high-lux extremes.

This work demonstrates how AI-based multi-objective optimization enables fair comparison of heterogeneous lighting technologies and provides guidelines for energy-efficient and visually reliable automotive lighting design.

Keywords: Automotive lighting, Halogen, LED, Xenon, NSGA-II, Multi-objective optimization, Energy efficiency, Artificial intelligence.